

SYNTHESIS IN ACRIDINE SERIES. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF
5-N-SUBSTITUTED 1:9- AND 2:9-DICHLOROACRIDINES

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5-(*β*-Diethyl-amino-*α*-methylbutyl)-amino-2:9- and -1:9-dichloroacridines have been synthesised by cyclisation of the amides obtained from the required amine and the acid chloride of 5:2'-dichloro-(I) and 6:2'-dichloro- (II) diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid respectively.

In a previous communication (Patel and Nargund, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 770) synthesis of 3:7- and 3:9-dichloro-5-N-substituted acridine derivatives has been described. In continuation of this series, the present paper deals with the synthesis of the corresponding 1:9- and 2:9-dichloroacridine derivatives.

The Ullmann condensation of 4:2-dichlorobenzoic acid with *o*-chloroaniline failed to afford the expected 5:2'-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (I), when the condensation was attempted in presence of various solvents like amyl alcohol, xylene and nitrobenzene at temperatures varying from 120° to 200°. Ultimately, when the reaction was carried out in absence of a solvent using *o*-chloroaniline in excess, (I) was obtained in about 50% yield. In this connection it would be interesting to note that Whitmore *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1596) reported that 2':4-dichlorobenzoic acid, on similar condensation with *m*-chloroaniline, using methylcyclohexanol as solvent, furnished 5:3'-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid in only about 6% yield.

6:2'-Dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (II) was obtained on condensation of 3-chloroanthranilic acid with *o*-chloro-iodobenzene, using the latter in excess in place of a solvent. Chaudhry and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1951, **19**, 65, 68) have synthesised 3-chloroanthranilic acid (III) by two different methods, viz., (i) by oxidation

of 7-chloroisatin and (ii) by Hoffmann's degradation of 3-chlorophthalimide. The method described here is a modification of the latter method and in this the phthalamic acid, obtained on treatment of 3-chlorophthalic anhydride with ice-cold liquor aminouia, was subjected to Hoffmann's degradation to furnish (III) as the only product of the reaction. This indicated that the anhydride ring opened up only in one way, affording 2-amido-3-chlorobenzoic acid (IV); on opening in the other manner, 2-amido-6-chlorobenzoic acid (V) would have been obtained and which on Hoffman's degradation would have furnished 6-chloroanthranilic acid (VI).

5:2'-Dichloro- and 6:2'-dichloro-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids on reaction with phosphorus oxychloride afforded the corresponding dichloroacridones, instead of the expected corresponding 5-chloroacridine derivatives. Hence, the facile method (Magidson and Grigorovsky, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 396) of obtaining 5-N-substituted aminoacridine derivatives by condensing the corresponding 5-chloroacridine derivative with the required amine was not applicable. 1:9-Dichloro- and 2:9-dichloro-5-N-substituted acridine derivatives, described in this communication, were therefore obtained from the acid chlorides of (II) and (I) respectively, and the required amines were isolated as hydrochlorides. In some cases the hydrochlorides were obtained as slightly sticky solids, due to the traces of moisture associated with them and had to be treated by heating them under reduced pressure in order to obtain the product suitable for characterisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

5:2'-Dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—When the condensation of 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid (1M) with *o*-chloroaniline (1M) was carried out in presence of potassium carbonate (1 M) and a trace of Cu powder and solvents like amyl alcohol and xylene at temperatures from 120° to 150°, and nitrobenzene at higher temperatures up to 200°, the reaction in each case failed, 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid having been recovered unchanged. The condensation was successfully carried out as detailed below.

To the dry voluminous precipitate of the potassium salt of 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid, obtained by refluxing a mixture of 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid (10 g.), potassium carbonate (10 g.) and benzene (10 c. c.) and subsequent removal of benzene by distillation at 100°, *o*-chloroaniline (30 c. c.) and a trace of copper powder were added and the resulting mixture was heated at 165-70° for 3 hours. Excess of *o*-chloroaniline was removed by steam-distillation and the residual solution, after treatment with charcoal, furnished 5:2'-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid as a light coloured powder on acidification; yield (crude), 7 g. It crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish needles, m.p. 228-29°. (Found: Equiv., 284; N, 4.85; Cl, 25.5. $C_{13}H_9O_2NCl_2$ requires equiv., 282; N, 4.9; Cl, 25.2%).

5:2'-Dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid chloride was obtained by heating the above acid (1 part) and thionyl chloride (5 parts) for half an hour and on subsequent distillation of the excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure. The crude acid chloride was sufficiently pure for its use in the subsequent operation. It crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 100-101°. (Found: Cl, 35.7. $C_{13}H_8ONCl_2$ requires Cl, 35.4%).

2:9-Dichloro-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine hydrochloride was prepared by cyclisation of the acid anide obtained on reacting the above mentioned acid chloride with δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine, following the method described in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). The hydrochloride was dissolved in a minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and the solution was diluted with three times the quantity of acetone and kept overnight, when the hydrochloride separated as a yellow solid. Due to traces of moisture in it, it could not be powdered well for the determination of its m.p. and so it was dried by heating it at 80°/50 mm for half an hour; m.p. of the dried sample, 165-70° (decomp.). The sample was used for analysis. (Found: N, 7.9; Cl, 28.1. $C_{22}H_{23}N_3Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires N, 8.1; Cl, 27.8 %).

2:9-Dichloro-5(γ -morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride was obtained similarly from 5:2'-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic chloride and γ -morpholinopropylamine. It crystallised from alcohol-acetone mixture in yellow granules, m.p. 245-47° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.9; Cl, 31.5. $C_{20}H_{22}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 9.0; Cl, 30.8%).

3-Chlorophthalamic Acid (2-Amido-3-chlorobenzoic Acid).—3-Chlorophthalic anhydride (1 g.), obtained by treating 3-chlorophthalic acid with acetic anhydride (Chaudhry and Nargund, *loc. cit.*), was stirred in ice-cold liquor ammonia (3 c.c.) till it dissolved. This solution was acidified with HCl and after some time the acid slowly crystallised out from the acidified solution in small white plates, m.p. 235-37°. (Found: Equiv., 194; Cl, 17.6. $C_8H_6O_3NCl$ requires equiv., 199; Cl, 17.7%).

Hoffmann's Degradation of 3-Chlorophthalamic Acid: Formation of 3-Chloroanthranilic Acid.—3-Chlorophthalamic acid (2.5 g.) was dissolved in ice-cold N-KOH solution (25 c.c.) and then mixed with a solution of bromine (1 c.c.) in 25 c.c. of the same alkali solution, kept cool in an ice-bath. To this further quantity KOH solution (25 c.c.) was added and the resulting mixture was stirred for some time. The reaction flask was then removed and the temperature was slowly raised to 80°, after which heating was continued for half an hour. The reaction mixture was then cooled and just neutralised with calculated quantity of 2N-HCl and cooled in an ice-bath when 3-chloroanthranilic acid slowly separated out. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in pale yellow plates, m.p. 183°, yield 1 g. (Chaudhry and Nargund, *loc. cit.*, record the same melting point). (Found: Equiv., 168; Cl, 20.4. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_2NCl$: Equiv., 171; Cl, 20.7%).

6:2'-Dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—A mixture of 3-chloroanthranilic acid (5 g.), potassium carbonate (4 g.) and benzene (10 c.c.) was refluxed for half an hour and the benzene was removed by distillation. To the residue *o*-chloriodobenzene (30 c.c.) and a trace of copper powder were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed at 165-70° for 3 hours. Excess of *o*-chloriodobenzene was removed by steam-distillation and the dark coloured solution after treatment with charcoal was filtered and acidified to obtain 6:2'-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid as a pale yellow solid. It crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow small needles, m.p. 176-78°, yield 6 g. (Found: Equiv., 280; N, 4.8. $C_{13}H_8O_2NCl_2$ requires equiv., 282; Cl, 25.2%).

6:2'-Dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic chloride was obtained from the above acid on treatment with thionyl chloride. It crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow plates, m.p. 89-90°. (Found: Cl, 35.7. $C_{13}H_8ONCl_2$ requires Cl, 35.4%).

1: 9-Dichloro-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine hydrochloride was obtained, as indicated above, starting with 6:2'-dichlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic chloride. The hydrochloride, which separated out as a yellow solid from a mixture of alcohol-acetone, could not be powdered well. It was therefore dried at $50^{\circ}/50$ mm. This sample melted at $155-60^{\circ}$ (decomp.) and the same used for analysis. (Found: N, 7.85; Cl, 28.0. $C_{22}H_{29}N_3Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires N, 8.1; Cl, 27.8%).

1: 9-Dichloro-5-(γ -morpholinopropyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride was obtained by similarly using γ -morpholinopropylamine. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow crystalline powder, m.p. $232-34^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 8.8; Cl, 31.3. $C_{20}H_{23}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 9.0; Cl, 30.8%).

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